

Question raised by requestor

In connection with the implementation of the Government Regulation on the establishment of conditions for the implementation of the Animal Welfare measures, we are preparing methodologies for good husbandry practice in the field of animal welfare with a focus on environmental enrichment, and that is why I would like to ask you to provide suitable studies, recommendations or methodologies for cattle. Specifically, the location, frequency of inspection and maintenance of gossipers, rinsing tubs in the stable and appropriate hoof disinfectants.

In addition, the guidelines will cover the housing of individual calves, particularly where less than six calves are housed.

Recommendation/studies on other environmental enrichment for cattle is welcomed.

Clarification was made regarding the terms 'gossiper' and 'rinsing tubs', which refer to a mechanical grooming brush for scratching cattle and appropriate hoof care namely a disinfection foot bath, respectively.

Answer

EURCAW *Ruminants & Equines* received your question 28 February 2023.

Several of your questions will shortly be addressed in upcoming reviews, or are already addressed in fact sheets.

Enrichment

Regarding enrichment that can be used for cattle, we refer to the following reviews (due to be published):

- Environmental enrichment in ruminants and equines: Introduction, soon available [here](#);
- Relational enrichment in ruminants and equines, soon available [here](#);
- Sensory and feeding enrichment in ruminants and equines, soon available [here](#);
- Physical and occupational enrichment in ruminants and equines, soon available [here](#);
- EURCAW *Ruminants & Equines* will publish a thematic fact sheet on enrichments specific to cattle in 2023.

Mechanical grooming brushes

Regarding mechanical grooming brushes, we refer to the review (due to be published, same as above):

- Sensory and feeding enrichment in ruminants and equines, soon available [here](#);

EURCAW *Ruminants & Equines* will provide further details about the use of brushes in a separate answer.

Individual housing of calves

Regarding the individual housing of calves, we refer to the following factsheets:

- Thematic factsheet – Visual and tactile contact in individually housed calves; available [here](#);
- Indicator factsheet – Visual and tactile contact in individually housed calves; available [here](#).

Provision of hoof care

Regarding the provision of hoof care, EURCAW *Ruminants & Equines* will publish a factsheet in 2024.

EURCAW *Ruminants & Equines* provides a 'Questions to EURCAW' (Q2E) service for official inspectors and policy workers. Please, send us an email with your question at info@eurcaw-ruminants-equines.eu